

OVERCOMING COMMON CHALLENGES IN LEARNING ENGLISH

Kuchimova Shohistabonu Najmiddin qizi

The student of Asian International University

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Abstract. This paper explores the common challenges faced by learners of English as a Second Language (ESL) and English as a Foreign Language (EFL), and investigates effective strategies to overcome them. We delve into hurdles such as: fear of making mistakes, lack of confidence, limited vocabulary, grammar complexities, and difficulties with pronunciation. The paper emphasizes the importance of individual learning styles and motivation, highlighting the role of technology, interactive learning environments, and authentic materials in facilitating language acquisition. Furthermore, we analyze the significance of cultural immersion, consistent practice, and effective feedback mechanisms in boosting fluency and confidence. Ultimately, this paper proposes a multifaceted approach to English language learning, advocating for a combination of traditional and innovative methods to empower learners and maximize their potential for success.

Key words: language, foreign language, challenges, vocabulary, motivation, resources, success, overcome, rewarding, opportunities, discipline, productivity.

ПРЕОДОЛЕНИЕ РАСПРОСТРАНЕННЫХ ПРОБЛЕМ ПРИ ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматриваются распространенные проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются изучающие английский как второй язык (ESL) и английский как иностранный язык (EFL), и изучаются эффективные стратегии их преодоления. Мы углубляемся в такие препятствия, как: страх совершить ошибку, неуверенность, ограниченный словарный запас, грамматические сложности и трудности с произношением. В статье подчеркивается важность индивидуальных стилей обучения и мотивации, выделяется роль технологий, интерактивных учебных сред и аутентичных материалов в содействии освоению языка. Кроме того, мы анализируем значение культурного погружения, последовательной практики и эффективных механизмов обратной связи для повышения беглости и уверенности. В конечном счете, в этой статье предлагается многогранный подход к изучению английского языка, выступающий за сочетание традиционных и инновационных методов для расширения возможностей учащихся и максимального увеличения их потенциала для достижения успеха.

Ключевые слова: язык, иностранный язык, проблемы, словарный запас, мотивация, ресурсы, успех, преодоление, вознаграждение, возможности, дисциплина, производительность.

Introduction: We are living in modern era, so there are a lot of language we may count . It is shown that 7000 languages spoken by people. But nowadays about 20 % of people speaks in English language. Because English provides them global communication and they can enhance their skill for modern connection between foreign people. And now we can counter this to various fields such as technology, science, business development or tourism industry. Especially, language of English is a key for future success and opens many doors for individual. Learning

language is not easy for everyone, because we did not face with this language before. It is significant to find out the challenges to struggle with them in order to do best. So, that time we can outcome effectively our challenges. There are some ways we should look at and how to tackle down with them.

1. Lack of Valuable Resources and Materials.

It is important to find reliable sources while learning English language. We can see there a lot of sites, but we should find one of them that suits us.

Start by more reputable language learning websites, apps, dictionaries, bots and etc. Look for more understandable sources which can give more information which is easy to understand and with more interactive activities which they help us to practice our knowledge.

Also, most important for us to join online platforms that can give more opportunities to increase our level. Because there are will more foreign people and they can give us more inquiries about their culture and country even about their people's way of understanding or thinking. Learning with foreign people help you to increase your level in high-quality.

2. Overcoming fear of speaking and building strong confidence.

Many languages learners face fear of speaking in front of audience and also, they have fear of making mistakes. And these cannot help to progress and increase their fluency.

In the beginning of the everything seems to us a little bit challenging. But doing errors is natural process of learning other language. We can learn foreign language by doing many remarkable mistakes and by analyzing them.

We should practice our language regularly even with our friends or teachers, but most effective one is to speak with native speakers and fellow learners. Because that time you can give a lot of information and share your ideas in supportive atmosphere.

3. Grammar and sentences structures.

Grammar seems to us a bit more complex, but is the same for native speakers. But Grammar is the most important part of learning language effectively.

To overcome this challenge, we should have foundation of grammar. They should start by learning with simple rules which more understandable for everyone and then they should conduct with complex rules.

To read more from English books, stories, journals and articles can help them to know about variety of words and sentences and also structures which is useful for them. Additionally, feedback from tutors and native people will be more beneficial to escalate the limit of knowledge base.

4. Vocabulary acquisition and techniques.

It is important for learners to have valuable and variety of words to use. Because only words can make our sentences colorful. We also should know how to utilize it in different way. And that time we need techniques and methods which is help for us to learn by heart.

One effective method to learn new vocabulary is to use every word into our daily life. For example, flashcards and apps which is help for us to review new words. Also, to write on the notebooks regularly enhance expend of our knowledge.

Additionally, make a sentence with new words also improve our vocabulary level. Also, to learn new words with definition can increase our thoughts and we know about many synonyms related to new vocabulary. This is the most effective way to learn by heart.

5. **Difficulty with pronunciation with strange language.**

Another common threat of learning language is pronunciation. Because of compound of English Grammar, many beginners face difficulty with pronunciation of words and accent.

To improve our pronunciation as native, we must watch several interviews from foreign people or listen podcasts and English songs. Also mimicking their words and intonation can produce the correct sounds.

But we should suggest that shadowing is most useful method to learn language effectively. Because we heard from many people that they grow their speech and pronunciation with help of shadowing method.

Additionally, we can improve our pronunciation with online apps such as Hello Talk, Duolingo, Alfa pt. And you can give from them more reliable feedback to improve your speech in advanced one.

6. **Lack of Motivation and discipline.**

Another hurdle that learners face is lack of motivation. Motivation plays crucial role in among learners. While learning we may encounter many problems and stress, and that time we need motivation for continuing our ambition. Without motivation it can be difficult for us make a progress.

But first of all, we need to set right goals and be motivated any time. Because, clear goals can lead to right way and with your ambitions you can achieve more thing easily. For example, rewarding yourself to the end of the achievement can improve your energy and confidence.

Also, to create clear schedule to help for you be productive and you can make progress faster with your right discipline.

Our ability to handle life's challenges is a measure of our strength of character.

Learning a language is a rewarding and challenging adventure that can change one's life. It's evidence of your dedication, tolerance, and tenacity. Speaking another language improves social and professional relationships while providing opportunities for personal development and cultural exploration. You may confidently navigate your language learning journey and take advantage of the amazing advantages that come with multilingualism by being aware of typical language learning obstacles and using effective ways to overcome them. Ultimately, the difficulties you face are only stepping stones on your way to becoming an expert language learner.

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